

Agricultural Knowledge Innovation System (AKIS) Analysis

AKIS Analysis

Deliverable 2.3

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Executive Summary

Organic Farming Innovations Network Europe –OH-FINE has a duration of 48 months, starting from the 1st of November 2024, and is funded by the European Union in the framework of Horizon Europe, the European Union's Research and Innovation Programme 2021-2027, and by SERI, the Swiss Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation. The project is coordinated by the Institute of Natural Resources and Agrobiology of Salamanca (IRNASA), which is part of the Spanish National Research Council (CSIC). The project focuses on empowering European farmers by advancing and sharing sustainable organic farming knowledge and solutions that align with farmer capabilities, consumer demands, and evolving food market trends. The project involves 18 partners from 9 countries.

This task (2.3) undertakes an assessment of the function and structure of the Agricultural Knowledge Innovation System (AKIS) that exists in each of the five partner regions (Spain, Bulgaria, Lithuania, Poland and Ireland), with the objective of comparing the level of support provided to the OH-FINE farmer cohorts (in-conversion to organic, post conversion and conventional farmers). The hypothesis for this research is that there may be differences in the type and extent of support provided by the AKIS across the three farmer cohorts and across the partner regions. The analysis involved undertaking farmer surveys, focus groups and social network mapping workshops that included farmers and stakeholder from the policy/regulation, research, intermediary (adviser) and enterprise (market) actor groups within the AKIS in each partner region. The findings support and inform the project and task hypotheses, demonstrating heterogeneity in engagement with AKIS stakeholders across partner regions and farmer cohorts.

Initial findings from the social network mapping process are as follows:

- In-conversion and post-conversion farmers show more frequent interaction with all specified AKIS actors in comparison with conventional farmers
- Conventional farmers identify very limited interaction with Organic Certification bodies while in-conversion and post-conversion farmers demonstrate very high levels of interaction with Organic Certification bodies
- There are differences across countries in terms of interaction with specified AKIS actors (for example: all three Polish and Irish cohorts identify regular interaction with their respective national advisory services while all three cohorts in Spain, Lithuania and Bulgaria identify limited interaction with their respective national advisory services)
- Bulgarian farmers have the highest levels of interaction with other AKIS actors in the conventional cohort as well as the in-conversion farmer cohort. Lithuanian farmers have the highest levels of interaction with other AKIS actors in the post-conversion farmer cohort. Most relationships between farmers and other AKIS stakeholders across the three farmer cohort groups and across countries have multiple natures (i.e. funding, information, service provision, flow of physical products and regulation). and are bi-directional (flow both towards farmers from other AKIS actors and flow from farmers towards other AKIS actors).

- Across the country contexts, weaker / infrequent relationships tend to be less multi-natured and tend to be one directional (mostly towards farmers from other AKIS actors).
- Frequency of interaction between AKIS stakeholders does not indicate a positive relationship. Farmers may interact regularly with certain actors (e.g. Organic Certification bodies) but do not necessarily regard their interaction as positive or useful. Farmers may also interact with certain stakeholders because they have limited other options or are not sure who to interact with instead. This is often the case when farmers are looking for information on organic production or information on compliance with certification standards.
- Farmers have different perspectives on the frequency, nature and direction of their relationships with other AKIS stakeholders in comparison with the perspective of other AKIS stakeholders.

DRAPF

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1. Introduction

The OH-FINE project brings together farmers, advisors, researchers, and policymakers to better understand how knowledge, support services, and innovation systems can help organics and sustainable farming practices to thrive. As part of this project, a series of workshops were planned and executed to better understand how farmers are connected to key actors and institutions in the agrifood sector in the selected partner regions. This includes advisory services, cooperatives, certification bodies, researchers, input suppliers, processors, and others. The input from both farmers and the wider network of AKIS actors helps identify what is working well in terms of innovation support services and knowledge for organic and sustainable farming, what needs improvement, and where there may be gaps or barriers in access to support and information.

1.1. Purpose of the document

This document describes the processes undertaken to collect and analyse the data required. The workshops and subsequent analysis explore how farmers interact with different organisations and services, how they learn and adopt new practices, and how these networks can support or hinder conversion to organic production, using social network analysis techniques. The focus is on the comparative environments for innovation across both participating regions and farmer cohorts (conventional, in-conversion and post-conversion).

This work will also contribute to later project activities and will be used as a baseline to compare against a subsequent summative evaluation, thus contributing to WP 8 and WP 9. Task 8.2 is a follow-up social-network mapping of the structure and function of the organic in-conversion AKIS in case study regions which will be undertaken to assess changes in the AKIS since the initial data collection in Task 2.3 (as outlined in the remainder of this report). Task 9.1 will provide follow-on data collection and analysis to assess changes in the AKIS since the initial overall AKIS data collection in T2.3 as well as collating cross-region information on the overall organic AKIS collected in T2.3 and 8.2 to draw conclusions on changes in the post-conversion AKIS and the structure and functioning of the overall organic AKIS and farmer social networks from the perspectives of in-conversion, post-conversion and conventional farmers.

2. Process for conducting and documenting social network workshops

The “OH-FINE Baseline Survey of Case Study Farms” questionnaires were distributed and initially completed by 80 case study farmers across the five partner countries prior to the Social Network mapping workshops, which took place between July and September 2025. The survey included a question related to mapping the Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation System (AKIS). Farmers were asked how often they engage with different key actors within their national context (Figure 1). Table 1 shows the breakdown of farmer responses to the baseline survey.

Note: Additional survey responses for the OH-FINE baseline survey were collected over the period July - October 2025, with a total of 103 responses across the five partner countries (Conventional: 26 responses; In-conversion: 51; post-conversion: 26). These

expanded survey responses will be included in future WP activities as well as other, additional project outputs (e.g. future academic journal articles).

Table 1. Breakdown of initial survey responses across the five partner countries, representing the three defined farmer cohorts; used for the development of a priori Social Network maps

Country	Conventional	In-conversion	Post-conversion	Total (country)
Poland	3	8	2	13
Ireland	3	4	3	10
Lithuania	5	9	5	19
Bulgaria	5	10	6	21
Spain	3	9	5	17
Total (cohort)	19	40	21	

Q.2. How often do you engage with the following people / groups? 1 = Never; 2 = Rarely; 3 = Occasionally; 4 = Often; 5 = Very Often

	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5	N/A
	Never				Very Often	
National advisory service	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5	
Private consultant	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5	
Organic Certification body	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5	
Farm Lobby Group	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 5	
Farmer network (e.g. discussion group, WhatsApp group)	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 5	
Agricultural cooperative or producer group	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 5	
Research institutions	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Commercial input suppliers	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5	
Product buyers (e.g. processors, retailers, direct sales/consumers)	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 5	
Farmers in other countries	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Environmental groups (e.g. non-government organisations (NGOs))	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 5	
Education or training bodies	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5	
Ministry of Agriculture	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5	
Environmental Regulatory bodies (e.g. water, climate, biodiversity)	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Land use interest groups (e.g. recreation, hunting, tourism)	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 5	
Other (please state _____)	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5	

Information on how you think about sustainable farming practices will help us to provide more targeted information to farmers.

Figure 1: Excerpt from OH-FINE baseline survey showing the AKIS question which formed the basis of the a priori maps for the Social Network mapping workshops

The results from this survey question were used to generate a priori, ego-centric social network maps from the perspectives of farmers. Maps were created for each farmer cohort (conventional, in-conversion and post-conversion) in each partner country, leading to a total of 15 unique maps across the project. The maps presented an aggregated interaction score, based on the survey responses collected from farmers, for each listed actor in Figure 1. The frequency of interaction was indicated by the aggregated score as well as colour and line thickness. The three elements used in the maps (interaction score, colour and line thickness) communicate the same message (frequency of interaction between farmers and other AKIS actors) but this was necessary to ensure that the maps were easily readable for facilitators and participants.

Figure 2: Depiction of the graduated colours, interaction scores (1 [never] to 5 [very often] based on Q2 of the Oh-FINE baseline survey and arrow thickness used to represent the frequency of interaction of farmers with the range of AKIS actors

3. A priori Social Network maps

Based on the survey responses, the following 15 a priori maps were developed ahead of the respective workshops which took place in each partner country.

Note: CO = conventional; IC = in-conversion; PC = post-conversion

3.1. Poland

3.2. Ireland

3.3. Lithuania

3.4. Bulgaria

3.5. Spain

Initial observations on a priori maps suggest the following:

- In-conversion and post-conversion farmers show more frequent interaction with all specified actors in comparison with conventional farmers,
- Conventional farmers identify very limited interaction with Organic Certification bodies while in-conversion and post-conversion farmers demonstrate very high levels of interaction with Organic Certification bodies,
- There are differences across countries in terms of interaction with specified actors (for example, all three Polish and Irish cohorts identify regular interaction with their respective national advisory services while all three cohorts in Spain, Lithuania and Bulgaria identify limited interaction with their respective national advisory services),
- Bulgarian farmers have the highest levels of interaction in the conventional cohort as well as the in-conversion cohort. Lithuanian farmers have the highest levels of interaction in the post-conversion cohort.

4. Social Network Mapping Workshop design

The Social Network Mapping workshops were designed to be interactive and collaborative processes where farmers and the wider AKIS actors could assess their interactions with one another. This provides useful insights for researchers on how knowledge flows between actors and where there may be bottlenecks or missing links between actors.

Project partners were asked to invite two core groups of participants (in line with the structure of the AKIS a priori maps):

1. Farmers from each OH-FINE cohort (2 x conventional, 4 x in-conversion and 2 x post-conversion/organic farmers)
2. Two representatives from each of the four main AKIS actor groups i.e. policy/regulation, research, advisory and market/enterprise. The range of actors participating included:
 - a. National advisory service
 - b. Private consultants
 - c. Organic certification bodies
 - d. Farm Lobby groups
 - e. Farmer lobby groups or cooperatives
 - f. Research institutions
 - g. Any other interested actors listed in the OH-FINE Baseline Survey of Case Study Farms (Question 2 – Figure 1)

Project partners received an information note which could be shared with farmers (and other actors) prior to the workshop which outlined the content and process of the workshop.

The workshops were organised and facilitated by staff of the project partner institutions. Each workshop began with a short powerpoint presentation giving overview of the project, the workshop tasks and outlining how the maps were generated. The workshops were divided into two parts:

4.1. Part 1: Reflection on and validation of a priori maps

Ask farmers and stakeholders to (separately) reflect on maps for conventional, in-conversion and post-conversion farmers. Specifically, participants were asked to reflect on the nature and direction of farmers' interactions with different AKIS actors. Two key questions were posed to participants:

1. Do the maps accurately reflect farmers' interactions with different groups / individuals?
2. What is the nature/ direction of farmers' interactions with different groups/individuals?

Validation of the a priori maps

- Workshop participants were divided into a farmer group and a stakeholder group. These groups were facilitated separately to analyse and each group validated the three a priori farmer maps (conventional, in-conversion and post-conversion) for their respective countries
- The three a priori maps plus legend map (see Annex A) were printed in A1 size and displayed on the walls. Notes were be made directly to maps by facilitators and workshop participants
- Audio recordings using smart phones were made for each group.
- The two groups (farmer group and stakeholder group) worked separately to validate and adjust the maps according to the:
- Strength of relationships: confirming that the associated number for each stakeholder group represented in the map is correct
- Type of relationship: Add to analysis by adding direction and colour coded arrows that capture five defined relationship types
 - Funding - schemes, supports (Black arrow)
 - Provision of information - training, advice, information (Green arrow)
 - Provision of services - knowledge/financial/physical services (Blue arrow)
 - Flows of physical product (Red arrow)
 - Regulation - inspection/audit (Yellow arrow)
- Direction of relationship: include arrows (can be one- or two-way arrows).

Figure 3. Example presented to workshop participants on how to provide input on the nature and direction of relationships between farmers and other AKIS actors.

In the example above, farmers have a weak / infrequent relationship with agricultural cooperatives or producer groups. Farmers rarely interact with cooperatives as indicated by the light green shading and thin connecting line. The farmers deliver physical products to the cooperative (e.g. milk) and the cooperative provides farmers with information, training and services. These relationships are represented by the arrows and their corresponding colours and directions.

4.2. Part 2: Discussion between all AKIS representatives

Both groups come together to discuss key points of difference between farmers' and stakeholders' perceptions of farmers' connections to AKIS stakeholders.

Both sets of maps (maps with farmer input and maps with AKIS actor inputs) are presented to the entire workshop group (farmers and other AKIS actors) so that participants can observe and comment on differences between the two perspectives. The workshop facilitators prompted discussion using the following set of questions:

- Are there significant differences in the perceptions of farmers and stakeholders?
- Which relationships are working well to support innovation and why?
- Which are not working well / not supporting innovation and why?
- What relationships need to be improved (strengthened, changed, etc.)?
- Are there any missing connections (which actors) which would improve/support farmer innovation?

Following the workshop, facilitators took the following steps to capture the data collected through the workshop process:

- All final mapping workshop outputs photographed and uploaded to the OH-FINE project portal
- All note taking on responses to structured questions transcribed, translated and sent to Irish partners.
- Recordings (and transcriptions & translations) uploaded to the OH-FINE project portal

5. Workshop findings

The workshops yielded the following data sources which can be used to generate academic outputs (e.g. journal articles), policy recommendations and Work Package outputs as well as inform future Work Packages (e.g. Work Package 8) and project activities across multiple work packages going forward:

- Updated maps (to compare with a priori maps and update original survey findings) which can be used for Social Network analysis
- Recordings (farmer discussion; stakeholder discussion; full group discussion) with transcriptions and translations which can be used for qualitative data analysis (thematic analysis)
- High-level workshop take-aways (provided by each project partner) to complement other data sources and improve future workshops.

This being said, the data collection process from the workshops was not entirely uniform. Workshop participants engaged with the workshop materials differently — for example: some workshops facilitators asked the AKIS questions (section 4.2) methodically during the full group discussion (and recorded the responses) whereas other facilitators took a less structured approach to the discussion and allowed participants to freely discuss issues which they identified. Additionally, not all project partners were able to successfully record all segments of the workshops. As such, having multiple data sources helps triangulate the findings and provide stop-gaps for missing data. There are still opportunities to streamline data collection further in future Work Package activities.

In the sections that follow, the updated Social Network maps (with the nature and direction of interactions identified by workshop participants) for each farmer cohort in the respective countries, along with high-level takeaways from each workshop are presented.

Overall, the following high-level findings were uncovered across the five country workshops:

- Most relationships between farmers and other AKIS stakeholders across the three farmer cohort groups and across countries have multiple natures and are bi-directional.
- Across the country contexts, weaker / infrequent relationships tend to be less multi-natured (fewer arrows depicted) and tend to be one directional (towards farmers).
- Farmers have different perspectives on the nature and direction of their relationships with other AKIS stakeholders in comparison with AKIS stakeholders (i.e. the farmer group maps and other stakeholder group maps are not identical)
- The workshops provided an opportunity for farmers to think beyond their own individual experiences (which were captured in the a priori ego-centric maps). By placing all three farmer cohorts together, farmers were better able to think at a system-level. This also provided an opportunity for farmers to discuss differences across farming systems. This was further strengthened by inviting other (non-

farmer) AKIS actors to provide input, especially during the final group discussions.

- The OH-FINE baseline survey measures relationships using frequency (i.e. how often farmers interact with other actors) rather than strength (how strong / good farmers feel that their relationships with other actors are). Frequency was chosen as it seemed easier to respond to in a survey setting. During some of the workshops, farmers themselves discussed this distinction, highlighting that it is possible to have 'frequent but negative' relationships and that farmers may interact with others due to limited choice.

5.1. Poland

Map 1. Nature and direction of interactions between conventional farmers and other AKIS stakeholders.

Top map: farmers' perspectives, bottom map: other AKIS stakeholders' perspectives.

Map 2. Nature and direction of interactions between in-conversion farmers and other AKIS stakeholders.

Top map: farmers' perspectives; bottom map: other AKIS stakeholders' perspectives.

Map 3. Nature and direction of interactions between post-conversion farmers and other AKIS stakeholders.

Top map: farmers' perspectives; bottom map: other AKIS stakeholders' perspectives.

High-level workshop findings

- Cooperatives and producer groups are underdeveloped especially in organic farming
- There are weak connections between farmers and the Ministry of Agriculture.
- Also, stakeholders view national advisory services as an intermediary / extension of the Ministry (rather than separate AKIS actors)
- The role of public advisors in the transition to organic is key but farmers experience different levels of commitment, knowledge, experience etc. across regions
- There are limited private (paid) advisory services. These services are mostly used by conventional farmers (less used by in-conversion or post-conversion farmers)
- There appear to be no links between environmental NGOs and farmers which is different from other countries

5.2. Ireland

Map 1. Nature and direction of interactions between conventional farmers and other AKIS stakeholders.

Top map: farmers' perspectives; bottom map: other AKIS stakeholders' perspectives.

Map 2. Nature and direction of interactions between in-conversion farmers and other AKIS stakeholders.

Top map: farmers' perspectives; bottom map: other AKIS stakeholders' perspectives.

Map 3. Nature and direction of interactions between post-conversion farmers and other AKIS stakeholders.

Top map: farmers' perspectives; bottom map: other AKIS stakeholders' perspectives.

High-level workshop findings

- Organic farmers find it more challenging to find research/evidence based information on organic production in comparison with conventional farmers. Farmers often have to look abroad to find relevant information on organic farming
- There are stronger lobby groups and cooperatives for conventional farmers in comparison with organic farmers. The strength of cooperatives also differs across systems. For example, there is a strong dairy cooperative movement but much weaker cooperative movement for livestock or cereal farmers
- National advisory are more focused on providing information and less focused on providing services whereas private consultants are more focused on providing services – specifically scheme application support
- Conventional farmers appear to be more dependent on/ connected to the Department of Agriculture than in-conversion and post-conversion farmers, although there was some disagreement among participants about this.

5.3. Lithuania

Map 1. Nature and direction of interactions between conventional farmers and other AKIS stakeholders.

Top map: farmers' perspectives; bottom map: other AKIS stakeholders' perspectives.

Map 2. Nature and direction of interactions between in-conversion farmers and other AKIS stakeholders.

Top map: farmers' perspectives; bottom map: other AKIS stakeholders' perspectives.

Map 3. Nature and direction of interactions between post-conversion farmers and other AKIS stakeholders.

Top map: farmers' perspectives; bottom map: other AKIS stakeholders' perspectives.

High-level workshop findings

- Issues related to market opportunities, prices and purchase channels are important for all farmer cohorts
- Participants highlight the bureaucratic burden of transitioning from conventional to organic production
- Farmers feel that they are required to have different types of knowledge including organic production practices, legal knowledge, regulation & certification. This places a burden on farmers who feel they have limited time
- Farmers expressed the need to increase farmer involvement in public organizations activities and inter-institutional networks and increase the availability of knowledge for farmers

5.4. Bulgaria

Map 1. Nature and direction of interactions between conventional farmers and other AKIS stakeholders.

Top map: farmers' perspectives; bottom map: other AKIS stakeholders' perspectives.

Map 2. Nature and direction of interactions between in-conversion farmers and other AKIS stakeholders.

Top map: farmers' perspectives; bottom map: other AKIS stakeholders' perspectives.

Map 3. Nature and direction of interactions between post-conversion farmers and other AKIS stakeholders.

Top map: farmers' perspectives; bottom map: other AKIS stakeholders' perspectives.

High-level workshop findings

- According to stakeholders, farmers interact with stakeholders *more* than what farmers recorded on their maps (difference in perceptions across the two groups)
- Frequent interactions do not necessarily imply high quality of information. Farmers interact with some actors because they have limited choice (the examples of the Ministry of Agriculture and organic inspectors were highlighted)
- Some research institutes lack capacity to promote / implement knowledge at farm-level. Better scientific communication is needed to facilitate knowledge transmission to farmers
- The national advisory service lacks organic farming knowledge and skills but they have a strong presence across municipalities and thus an opportunity to reach many farmers
- Farmer networks, input suppliers and private consultants are considered more innovative actors within the system.

5.5. Spain

Map 1. Nature and direction of interactions between conventional farmers and other AKIS stakeholders.

Top map: farmers' perspectives; bottom map: other AKIS stakeholders' perspectives.

Map 2. Nature and direction of interactions between in-conversion farmers and other AKIS stakeholders. Top map: farmers' perspectives; bottom map: other AKIS stakeholders' perspectives.

Map 3. Nature and direction of interactions between post-conversion farmers and other AKIS stakeholders. Top map: farmers' perspectives; bottom map: other AKIS stakeholders' perspectives.

High-level workshop findings

- Farmers turn to certification bodies for advice on organics but not all farmers have a positive experience.
- Peer and informal networks are a key source of practical guidance on organics
- There is no comprehensive public advisory system supporting the transition to organic production or innovation
- Applied research is needed, specifically short-term, region-specific demonstration farms or trials. This should be driven by farmer demand and feed into larger, longer-term research
- Regional / local intermediaries are needed to transfer knowledge between farmers & other stakeholders.

6. Recommendations for Project Interventions and Future Work Packages

The survey responses for the OH-FINE baseline survey will be used as a baseline to compare against future evaluation which takes place in WP8 and WP9. Moreover, these future work packages included follow-up social network mapping to assess the changes in the innovation system over the course of the project. As such, the following recommendations may be useful for future workshop design within the project as well as other projects / initiatives to map social networks within the agricultural sector:

1. In terms of workshop design, separating farmers and other AKIS actors highlighted nuances in experiences which in turn generated a robust general discussion between all actors. Farmers also seem to be more comfortable providing input when only farmers and facilitators are in the room. Workshop facilitators could then mediate farmer input in the general discussion, leading to a more open discussion on the challenges facing farmers and other actors. Future workshops should take these experiences into account and should be designed to minimise power imbalances and create opportunities for all stakeholders to provide their perspectives
2. Developing a priori Social Network maps was useful both to introduce other project partners to the social mapping process as well as ensure that the workshop sessions themselves were focused on collecting input from participants rather than spending time generating maps from scratch
3. The team strongly recommended that future activities need to provide clear value for farmers —maximising the benefits and minimising the inconvenience for participating farmers. For example, the Irish team chose to locate the workshop on a research farm where researchers presented results of an organic beef finishing trial. This provided an important incentive for farmers to attend the event, especially those who were travelling far distances or foregoing farm activities. Similarly, the Bulgarian facilitators chose to host the workshop at a venue where innovative practices for cereals were being tested in order to maximise incentive for attendance.

7. Conclusion

The series of Social Network mapping workshops brought advisory services, cooperatives, certification bodies, researchers, input suppliers, processors, and farmers together to understand the nature of the interactions between AKIS stakeholders and how this impacts the transition to organic production. Overall, the workshops were highly interactive events and even enjoyable events for participants; workshop attendees all responded positively to the experience. The workshop design process aimed to simplify the Social Network mapping process to streamline the cross-country workshops and provide maximum opportunity for farmers to feel engaged in the process and provide in-depth input. Creating an engaging and collaborative environment during the respective workshops also helps to encourage greater farmer participation and openness.

Generally, stakeholders and farmers were able to agree on the final social network maps (although there was less consensus in the Bulgarian workshop). However, it is important to note that farmers in all partner countries have different perspectives on the frequency, nature and direction of their relationships with AKIS stakeholders in comparison with the perspective of other AKIS workshop participants. The workshops highlighted the difference in experiences across farmer cohorts (conventional, in-conversion and post-conversion), across countries and across farm systems (e.g. dairy vs. cereals).

Broadly speaking, in-conversion and post-conversion farmers demonstrate higher frequency of interaction with all specified AKIS actors in comparison with the conventional farmer cohort. Across the countries, interaction with specified AKIS actors varies. For example, all three Polish and Irish cohorts identify regular interaction with their respective national advisory services while all three cohorts in Spain, Lithuania and Bulgaria identify limited interaction with their respective national advisory services.

All workshops identified multi-natured and bi-directional relationships between farmers and other AKIS stakeholders in all three cohorts. Many interactions provide a subset and combination of the suggested nature of interactions (i.e. funding, information, service provision, flow of physical products and regulation). Across the country contexts, more infrequent relationships tend to be less multi-natured and tend to be one directional (mostly towards farmers from other AKIS actors). It should also be recognised that frequency of interactions does not automatically indicate a positive relationship between stakeholders.

The findings from this task will be further analysed to draw conclusions on the current state of the organic AKIS and provide a baseline to map the changes in the structure and functioning of the overall organic AKIS and country-level farmer social networks over the course of the OH-FINE project.

8. Annex A - Legend map

Presented to the workshop participants to show how to provide input on relationship direction and the nature of the relationship between farmers and other AKIS actors.

9. Annex B – Photo Gallery

Polish farmers providing input to a priori Social Network maps

Bringing Irish farmers and other AKIS stakeholders together for discussion, facilitated by project partner representative from Teagasc

Lithuanian stakeholders providing input to a priori Social Network maps

Bulgarian workshop participants, facilitated by project partner representative (FOA Bioselena). The workshop was also used as an opportunity to showcase innovation in grain farming techniques / varieties at the workshop venue

Spanish workshop participants discuss Social Network maps

Irish Social Network workshop combined with visit to organic beef finishing trials to maximise incentive for farmers to attend the event

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